

Performance of Laterite soil used as an adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals.

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Abstract:

Our society is very concerned about the rising levels of soil and ground water pollution brought on by anthropogenic percolation of heavy metals. Concentration of heavy metals are the major concern for the environment as they are toxic and non-biodegradable and having their high potential to pollute surface as well as underground water. Heavy Metals make the water unfit for plants and humans. It is discharged straight from zinc processing units, dyeing industries, galvanizing industries, and metal industries. etc. Different removal processes are applied to separate heavy metals from the effluents like phase separation, reverse osmosis, evaporation etc. However, these processes have some demerits, including a high reagent demand, erratic metal ion removal, the production of toxic sludge, etc. In this study, we have used adsorption process because it is easy to handle and simplicity and low cost. The research work is to determine the performance of laterite soil used as an adsorbent for removal of Zn & Cu. To evaluate the adsorption capacity of soil, adsorption isotherms and kinetic studies were carried out at different starting concentrations of adsorbate (5, 10 mg L⁻¹) at a constant pH of 8, with varied adsorbent doses (5, 10 g L⁻¹), and an equilibrium contact period of 120 minutes. The adsorbent capacity of the adsorption process was determined using the linear, Langmuir, and Freundlich isotherm models. The Langmuir isotherm at a soil dose of 5.0 g L⁻¹ best matched the results of the Zn adsorption test, with R²=0.922 and RMSE=0.000962. Similar patterns were revealed by the results of a Cu adsorption test with adsorbent dose of 5 g L⁻¹ having R²=0.989 and RMSE=0.000588.

Keywords: Adsorption; Heavy metals; Isotherm Studies; laterite soil.

1. Introduction

The soil and water are harmed by anthropogenic pollution, especially when untreated or improperly treated effluents are released into the lithosphere. Heavy metal pollution is a serious environmental concern since it is poisonous, non-biodegradable, and has a high potential to pollute both surface and groundwater. Subterranean water is unsuited for use by both people and plants. Typical sources of Cu and Zn-containing wastewater include mining, tanneries, metal plating, fertilizer, galvanizing, dyeing, and paper industries^{1,2,3}, as well as zinc processing facilities. Due to their high mobility and toxicity, Zn & Cu are the main focus of this study, as Cu is preferentially adsorbed and less affected by the other metals.⁴

Additionally, Zn is closely correlated with oxide and the carbon bound fraction in aqueous media. Strict limitations on the quality of wastewaters emitted have been devised due to their toxicity, carcinogenic nature, permanence, and potential to bio-accumulate⁵, as well as other factors. Examples of these limitations are those outlined by the WHO, US EPA, or EU. WHO advises that the concentrations of Cu and Zn in mining and electroplating effluent be less than 2.0 and 5.0 mg/L, respectively, while the US EPA has set limits of 1.3 and 1.7 mg/L respectively. Industrial wastewater becomes more toxic for receiving ecosystems when these

chemicals are present, upsetting the balance of aquatic life and having a detrimental impact on human health. Prior to being discharged into aquatic habitats, this requirement for their removal and reduction in accordance with the specifications of the acceptable standard is made. There are several ways to treat wastewater, but due to its effectiveness and simplicity of usage, adsorption is mostly used to remove or reduce the amount of heavy metals present in liquid effluents. The adsorbents employed for the adsorption of heavy metals can come from either mineral or organic sources, like activated carbon and bio-sorbents, or from organic sources, including natural zeolite, calcium silicate powders, and bio-sorbents. Due of its simplicity and inexpensive cost, we adopted the adsorption technique in this investigation. The specific objective of the study is to remove heavy metals by low cost adsorbent-laterite soil which is locally available in Durgapur.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection and Characterization of Adsorbent

The stone quarry of Kamalpur, which is close to Durgapur in West Bengal, India, was where the laterite soil sample was taken. The sample was obtained by auger boring from a depth of 2 meters, transported to the laboratory for its physico-chemical characteristics were ascertained in accordance with IS 2720.

2.2 Batch Adsorption Studies

At constant room temperature (32 ± 2 °C) and aerobic conditions, batch adsorption investigations were carried out by combining 10g of soil with 50ml of stock solution in a number of 100 ml conical flasks. To study the adsorption on soil, initial heavy metal concentration was selected to meet the optimum condition. The following criteria was selected i) the desired pH has selected by the batch test with varying pH, ii) The optimum time has selected by batch experiment with varying contact time and iii) For desired adsorbent dose, the batch test was done with varying adsorbent dose.

2.3 Adsorption Isotherm Studies

A buffer solution of NaOH was used to adjust the pH to 8 before conducting isotherm tests in a 100 ml conical flask at a constant room temperature with varied starting doses of 0.5, 1.0, 5.0, and 10.0 mg L⁻¹. Filtration of the mixture was done by using 0.22 milipore filter paper, and the filtered solution was evaluated using an atomic adsorption spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer). The following equation was used to calculate laterite soil's maximal heavy metal adsorption capacity.

$$Q_e = ((C_0 - C_e)V)/M$$

Where, Q_e = adsorption capacity (mg/g)

C_0 = Initial conc. Of solute (mg L⁻¹)

C_e = Conc. Of solute at equilibrium (mg L⁻¹)

M = Mass of adsorbent (gm)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Properties of Adsorbent

Table 1: Physical and Chemical Properties of Adsorbent

Physical Properties	Value
Specific Gravity	2.69
Bulk Density (g/cc)	1.25
Plastic Limit (%)	13.12
Plasticity Index (%)	12.88
Hydraulic Conductivity (cm/sec)	3.71×10^{-8}
pH	6.51
Total Porosity (%)	53.53
Organic Carbon (%)	0.55
Sand (%)	49
Silt (%)	39
Clay (%)	12
Max dry density (g/cc)	1.93
Natural Moisture Content (%)	12.61
Liquid Limit (%)	26

3.2 Batch Adsorption studies

In order to assess how well metals were mobilized from soil, batch adsorption studies were conducted. To meet the ideal and effective adsorption conditions, we first chose the appropriate pH, appropriate time, and appropriate adsorption dose to measure the rate at which heavy metals adsorb on soil. When the initial concentration and adsorbent dose were 10 mg L^{-1} and 10 g L^{-1} , respectively, with the ideal pH of 8, it was observed that the removal efficacy for both Zn & Cu gradually rose up to 120 minutes, at which point it stayed constant. This is because there were no adsorbent sites available at first, increasing the concentration gradient between the adsorbate in solution and the adsorbent surface. Therefore, during a contact time of two hours, the adsorbent is effective to remove almost 90% of heavy metals.

Fig-1: Kinetic Study (Initial concentration -10mg L⁻¹ and Adsorbent Dose-10g L⁻¹)

Fig-2: Effect of pH (Initial concentration- 10mg L⁻¹ and Adsorbent Dose-10g L⁻¹)

Fig-3: Effect of dose (Initial Concentration- 10mg L⁻¹ and pH- 8)

3.3 Batch Isotherm Studies

The graph displays the results of the Freundlich isotherm, Langmuir, and linear models that were used to explain the adsorption of heavy metals (Zn & Cu) in laterite soil. The isotherm parameters K_d , K_f , $1/n$, Q_{max} , b , RMSE and R^2 are summarized in Table No -2.

Fig4: Freundlich isotherm curve (10gm L⁻¹ of soil dose, pH 8.0, at RPM 150 at different concentration of Zn.)

Fig 5: Freundlich isotherm curve (10g l⁻¹ of soil dose, pH 8.0, at RPM 150 at varying concentration of Cu.)

Table 2: Isotherm Model constants for heavy metals.

Model Used for Zn	Isotherm Constant	R ²	Model Used for Cu	Isotherm Constant	R ²
Freundlich	1/n = 1.6945 mg L ⁻¹ K _f = 31.14mg kg ⁻¹	0.990	Freundlich	K _f = 21.25 mg kg ⁻¹ 1/n=1.4936	0.940
Langmuir	Q _{max} =416.67mg kg ⁻¹ b=1.33 L mg ⁻¹	0.920	Langmuir	Q _{max} =625m gm kg ⁻¹ b= 0.666	0.989
Linear	K _d =2078 L kg ⁻¹	0.910	Linear	K _d = 1224 L kg ⁻¹	0.690

From figures 4 and 5, as well as table 2, the test data were clearly well matched by the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm models, which Langmuir had higher coefficients of determination and smaller error values. But the isotherm model, with its larger R² and lower RMSE values, was the best fit for both Zn and Cu. Using the equation is shown below, the dimensionless separation factor (R_L) was used to predict the form of the Langmuir isotherm model.

$$R_L = 1 / (1 + bC_0)$$

The computed R_L values for Zn and Cu, which are within the range ($0 < R_L < 1$) and demonstrated that the capacity of laterite soil to adsorb heavy metals like zinc and copper is favourable, which were 0.069 and 0.13 respectively, Where b = constant associated with the free energy of adsorption and C_0 = initial concentration of heavy metals.

4. Conclusion

In the present study, two heavy metals Zn^{+2} and Cu^{+2} from aqueous solutions were almost eliminated by laterite soil. The highest removal of Zn^{+2} and Cu^{+2} were achieved at pH of 8 and soil doses of 10 g L^{-1} and 120 minutes of contact time. In such optimal conditions, the laterite soil has the capacity to extract more than 90% of Zn^{+2} and Cu^{+2} . The adsorption isotherm studies demonstrated that the Langmuir isotherm models was the best fit for removal of Zn^{+2} and Cu^{+2} with $R^2 = 0.9906$ and $RMSE = 0.054$ for Zn at 10 g L^{-1} soil dosage and $R^2 = 0.9912$ and $RMSE = 0.053$ for Cu at 10 g L^{-1} soil dose respectively. It may be inferred from this study that it was viable to remove heavy metal contamination from ground water. We can also draw the conclusion that it has a very high potential for usage as a landfill liner material.

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